

Survey and analysis on Heritage Buildings of various eras in perspective of Visualization and Preservation

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Abstract: West Bengal, specially its capital Kolkata as well as its surroundings areas carries age-old histories from Mughal era to European communities. These historic buildings possess collections of various articles which have some high heritage values. Proper restoration and preservation of those antique materials are essential. Effort has been undertaken at Government level, e.g., development of Archaeological Society of India, etc. There are many Heritage Buildings in and around Kolkata. For various reasons, e.g., obtaining permission etc. studies have to be limited upon some typical buildings only. This paper generally discusses on the antique collections, particularly of archives materials like paintings, sculptures, photographs, periodicals, costumes, curio pieces, etc. is a matter of serious investigation for prolonging the useful lifespan of physical items that hold outstanding records of the past wisdom.

Keywords: Preservation, Heritage Buildings, Visibility, Deterioration, Biodegradation, Fading

1. Introduction:

Most of the cultured nations around the world have some old buildings which have some Heritage significances. By studying and learning about the history it helps us to understand how to modernize the countries in the best way keeping the trail of local cultural heritage. These structures provide an insight into the history of the countries, showing how people even in and many centuries ago perused their lives. Many of these buildings have very beautiful architecture as well as some precious collections. It is very important to maintain these old collections.

Heritage Buildings are essential assets of an area because these comprise of various archival and rare collections of paintings, sculptures, photographs, coins, textiles, folk arts, periodicals, costumes, curio pieces, etc. So, preservation of antique collections is a matter of serious scientific investigation for prolonging the useful lifespan of physical items that hold outstanding records of the past wisdom to revisit and relook history of science and culture.

For visibility point of view proper lighting arrangement is also very important. Those places where adequate level of daylight cannot reach, artificial lights needed to be complemented partially or completely. Light, both natural and artificial, is one of the environmental factors that need to be controlled to achieve this goal for the preventive care of such important historic repositories . Therefore, Interior lighting design plays a significant role for achieving this goal. This approach follows specific scientific guidelines however it can be varied depending upon the designer's choice. Crucial selection of lamps and luminaires is very much important for proper visibility and to provide aesthetic look to match with the surrounding environment.

2. Survey on Heritage Buildings of various eras:

2.1 Bawali Raj Bari ^[1,2,3] :

2.1.1 Era: Palace of Bawali or Bawali Rajbari was erected in the later phase of medieval time of India , that is during the rule of Akbar, the Mughal Emperor.

2.1.2 Present Location: The Rajbari Bawali is set in a serene environment, away from the

chaos of the present capital city, Kolkata. Presently it is located at North Bawali, 24 Parganas (South), Kolkata.

2.1.3. Speciality of the Building: Around 250 years

Fig 1: Front view of Bawali Rajbari (Mughal Era)

ago, the amazing architectural masterpiece known as the Rajbari was constructed. More than that, it has established the ideal example in the revival and displaying of the traditional performing arts of Bengal. The building is made up of nice architecture, luxury, and history of the little hamlet of the south 24 parganas. In addition, the nearby village communities have a significant impact on promoting and encouraging the local arts and crafts.

2.2 Chandan Nagar Museum (Formerly Known as Chandan Nagar Governor House): ^[1,4]

2.2.1. Era: Chandan Nagar Museum has an important heritage significance during time of *French* colonial power in India.

2.2.2 Present Location: It is in the heart of Chandan Nagore and located on the Strand Road, west bank of Hooghly River which is 35 Km from Kolkata.

Fig 2: Front view of Chandan Nagar Museum (Portuguese era)

2.2.3 Speciality of the Building: Chandannagar was a French settlement established in 1673. The French influence in the area lasted until 1950 when it was integrated into the Indian Union. The museum building itself is a colonial-era structure, built in the

18th century and initially served as the residence of the French Governor-General, Joseph François Dupleix. The Chandannagar Museum was established to preserve the artifacts and history of the French colonial period in India. It houses a wide range of items including French antiques, cannons used in battles, and other memorabilia from the colonial period. In the nineteenth century, Lal Bahadur Shastri, the prime minister of India, and Pompier, the prime minister of France, founded it. It is a well maintained museums in that area. The museum primarily emphasises Chandannagar 's local history . The French furniture, French periodic administration, and Indian art and crafts galleries are the museum's main draws. The public opening of the museum and art gallery took place in 1956.

2.3 Sreerampore Church ^[1,5] :

2.3.1 Era: It is known as the Danish Church. This Heritage Building was one of the 100 buildings which constructed by the *Danish* management in between 1755 to 1845, at a time when the town was called Frederik Nagore.

Fig 3: Front view of Serampore St Olav Church (Dutch Era)

2.3.2 Present Location: It is located in Serampore, West Bengal just 24 kilometres from Kolkata.

2.3.3 Speciality of the Building: The Serampore College or the St. Olav Church was founded by William Carey, and Serampore was renowned for its elite educational institutions. The church was constructed in 1806 and features an enormous steeple as well as extensive British-style design as opposed to Danish-

style architecture. The church is highlighted by the Danish monarch Christian-VII's royal monogram. It has a cutting-edge sound system and is painted in its distinguishing pure white colour scheme.

2.4 Dhanyakuria Village Palaces ^[1,6]:

2.4.1 Era: Dhanyakuria turned into a proper settlement for living in 1742 when Jagannath Das settled with his family. Likewise, families of many purveyor like Mandal, Gaine, Sau and Ballabhs came and settled in the village during time of British Indian Jaminder period.

2.4.2 Present Location: It is a rural village, barely 52 kms away from Kolkata, in North 24 Parganas, that reminds the great lifestyle of Bengali Jaminders and affluent with neo-classical European touch and British influence.

2.4.3 Speciality of the Building: It is famous for Village palaces as well as art and crafts. It comprises with showpieces of fusion architecture. The palaces also highlight a fortune trading in jute, jaggery , salt , etc.

(i)

(ii)

Fig 4: Front view of (i) Gayen Bari and (ii) Ballav Bari (Jamindar Era in British period at Dhanyakuria West Bengal)

2.5 Jorasanko Thakurbari ^[1,7]:

2.5.1 Era: The Rabindra Bharti Museum, popularly known as “The Jorasanko Thakurbari” which was the home of the Thakur family. It was built by Prince Dwarkanath Tagore (grandfather noble laureate Sri Rabindranath Tagore) in the 18th century.

2.5.2 Present Location: Jorasanko Thakur Bari is the ancestral home of the Tagore family in Jorasanko, North Kolkata, West Bengal, India. At present it is located on the Rabindra Bharati University campus at Dwarakanath Tagore Lane Jorasanko, Kolkata .

2.5.3 Speciality of the Building: Visitors to the ancestral home can get a sense of how the home appeared when the Tagore family lived there. A meticulous restoration work has been done. The museum provides in-depth insights into the history of the Tagore family and is quite educational. Three separate galleries, manuscripts, books, and other heritage artefacts are also

included in the museum. The seven hundred artworks on display at this museum grab tourists' attention.

Fig 5: Front view of Jorasanko Thakurbari

3. Analysis of Heritage Buildings according to Survey:

3.1 Poor Visibility: -

Presentation is an easy term to understand, meant for effective communication. It is simply the visitors view of an exhibit either good or bad. Lighting is one of communication link between the objects and the observer. If proper colour components are not present in light, or if they are too strong or out of balance, it distorts the visual communication. **Poor quality of lighting arrangement** ^[7] **always creates poor exhibits!** Ignoring good lighting design, glare and reflection can make difficult to see even wonderful artefacts. Poor quality lighting will make artwork or exhibits dull, lifeless, or distorted. Colour rendering index (CRI) is a qualitative measurement of a light source. It reveals the colours of various objects faithfully compared with a natural light source. Light sources with a high CRI are desirable in colour- critical applications such as preventive care and art restoration. CRI measures – on a scale from 0 to 100 – light quality in relation to the eye's ability to see colours correctly. There is no standard guideline for an acceptable CRI, but Museum or Heritage Building lighting designers suggest 80 - 100 CRI to ensure that the colours can be visualized properly. Some times improper reflections from the surface causes visual obstructions as shown below:

Fig 6: Examples of poor visibility in different frames[1]

3.1.1 Example of some views due to Poor visibility^[1,9]:

➤ Unsatisfactory Illuminance level:

Uniform light distribution is very much important for a good and efficient Lighting design . In this area daylight entered from a glass window. So, illuminance level is very high near the window & the illuminance level of other area is low.

Fig 7: Museum Gallery at Chandan Nagar Museum showing the interior design

➤ Poor Luminaire condition :

Due to aging, condition of luminaire is very poor. So light distribution is not proper.

Fig 8 : Museum Gallery at Chandan Nagar Museum showing traditional lighting system

➤ Improper visualisation due to poor lighting arrangement:

Ambient and accent lighting concept is very much essential for this purpose. Actually ambient lighting can illuminate the whole area but it cannot focus sufficient light at specific object. Lighting design is very much essential to describe a room also feel its environment.

Fig 9: Art Gallery: Photographs at Sreerampore Church[1,5]

3.2 Deterioration of materials^[10] (Fading) :

Degradation of colour in textile and paper materials (displayed and stored in galleries) of a Heritage Building is a major problem now a day; it is well known that microorganisms are responsible for the deterioration and degradation of materials. Two major factors are responsible for the infest of microorganisms^[10] on artefacts, especially on paintings, are-the chemical nature of the substratum and the environmental conditions, such as the availability of nutrients, favorable environment conditions like humidity, temperature, etc. Microbial-induced deterioration effects on paintings can occur on both the front as well as their reverse side of the object. The degree of deterioration on the 'front side' depends on the painting medium while condition of the 'reverse side' depends on the nature and character of the support e.g. canvas, wood etc.

In case of oil paintings upon canvas it has to be seen that, the bio-deterioration process usually effects on the reverse side of the painting for the presence of support polymers, the glue etc in the canvas; components which is prone to act as substrates which accelerate microbial growth. The organic materials present at the front of the painting are susceptible to attack by some sort of microorganisms and transient airborne microorganisms too. Bacteria and fungi represent a major role in this sub aerial community which can accumulate or concentrate on the painted surface for a long period of time as spores. The further growth of these microorganisms can result for the detachment of the painting layer from the support like canvas or wood especially in paint kept under conditions of high humidity. For example, Painting of Monalisa has been conserved at constant 50% relative humidity at Louvre Museum. Moreover, the excretion of aggressive metabolic products like organic or inorganic acids and the additional production of extracellular enzymes that increase the possibility of loss of materials.

Fig. 10: Comparison between deterioration of colour[10]

3.3 Photochemical deterioration ^[11,12]:

In Historic building the environment, photochemical reactions upon artefacts are most likely to be initiated by UV radiation and the visible light too. Ultraviolet radiations nearly always accompany visible light, because it is produced by the sun and / or artificial light sources, such as fluorescent tubes and tungsten halogen bulbs.

- Photochemical reactions have sufficient energy to react with the original substance and produce further chemical change. This is a “chain reaction” as the light produces not just one chemical change but an entire series of them; and this phenomenon happens while the object is still exposed to light, and a chain reaction occurs at a rapid pace.
- The amount of damage depends not only on the spectrum quality of the light, but also on the intensity of light that falls on the material and time of exposure. It is remembering that some of these chemical reactions continue after the exposure has stopped. The deterioration reaction does continuous even when the material is placed in the dark.
- Deterioration of artefacts is due to photochemical reactions include: Dyes fading and changing colour. This is perhaps the obvious damage caused by natural or artificial light and Ultra Violet radiations (UV). It has been observed that the radiation has its great impact on the surface of the object, especially on paint layers for example, dyes on the exposed side of a carpets have been fade out, while dyes on the unexposed side appear to retain their original colour.

3.4 : Biodegradation ^[11,12,13]:

Bio deterioration may be defined as “any undesirable change in the properties of a material which is caused by the vital activities of living organisms”, as distinguished from changes produced by “chemical, mechanical, and physical influences”. Biological agents that produce deterioration are referred to as bio-deterioration, and these range from microorganisms like fungi to higher plants and to animals such as insects and rodents and many others.

Fig 11 : Example of biodegradation due to microorganism

Bio deterioration of cultural property is a major problem in almost all parts of the world. The art works and artefacts are constantly being destroyed by biological agents. Since Organic materials which are used for many traditional artefacts, are most vulnerable to biological attack and since the high heat and humidity can weaken organic materials and induce the growth and reproduction of bio deteriogens. It faces critical problems in protecting its cultural collections from bio deterioration. The effects of environmental conditions by bio deterioration on the artefacts are commonly observed in museum.

3.5 Craquelure :

A network of fine cracks or crackles ^[12] on the surface of a painting, mainly caused by shrinkage of paint layers or even varnish, but could also be a result of weakening of the ground and/or support. Generally, such types of problem occur due to excessive heat of artificial light sources and the exhibits suffer to a great extent. Electromagnetic waves mainly comprise with Visible light source, UV and IR radiations. The factors that exist as stated above, both UV and IR are responsible for this type of effects on all types of archival materials (it may reduced up to 50% than previous). This has been found in an European painting of the King at Rajbari

Museum of Mahishdal, Midnapur , located at very warm place. Photography was not allowed therein. However a sample is shown here.

Fig 13 : Example of craquelure[13]

3.5 Identification of some other practical problems in the study area: Antique and archival materials i.e. books, painting, textiles are damaged probably by UV radiation, heat generation from artificial light sources and fluctuations of environmental factors and its effects due to moisture :

- **Fading of Paintings materials:** In this picture it has been observed that Watercolour is faded drastically. This is mostly found when the watercolour is removed from its mount. The edges of the work, covered under frame etc. i.e. less exposed to light, often seem to have denser colour than the exposed part.

Fig 14: Art Gallery Photographs at Chandan Nagar Museum (Governor House)

- **Decolourisation & brittleness of Paper documents:** In this picture it can be observed that colour of paper documents turns to yellow, day by day due to environmental factors and biodegradation and it can't be handled or maintained properly due to its brittleness.

Fig 15: Art Gallery Photograph at Chandan Nagar Museum (Governor House)

- **Gradual deterioration and discolour of Textiles:** It is usually observed that cotton, wool and silk are all slowly affected by light including UV radiation. But the reactions they undergo are different, as they are of differing in chemical compositions. Cotton will react like paper as both are cellulose-based ; it will darken and become brittle. Both Wool as well as Silk are composed of proteins. It is usually observed that both wool and silk are bleached by visible light, and turns to yellow when exposed to UV radiation; and changes occur in oil paintings. This can include the discoloration of varnishes and grossly disturb the equilibrium of the paint - layer and decrease the glossiness of paints. The changes also involve complex interactions among oils, pigments and varnishes.

Fig 16: Present status of Textiles & Photographs in Dhanyakuria Village palaces

4. Survey & Analysis report on Heritage Buildings

From the above survey it has been observed that majority of the Heritage Buildings within West Bengal are not properly illuminated and artefacts are not conserved too. The lighting design of Heritage Building as well as Museum has changed enormously over the last fifty years. Initially most galleries were designed by utilization of daylight. But due to urbanization adequate daylight is not available in entire the building. For this reason, uses of artificial lamps is very much essential, which are more technically upgraded ^[14] at present. In earlier days incandescent lamp are used which is obsolete now a day due to its least energy efficiency compare to other newly developed lamps. Approximately most of the energy (90%) that is consumed in an incandescent lamp is release in the form of heat while only 10% is converted to visible light. Then low wattage sodium vapour, mercury vapour and incandescent (PAR) lamps are introduced to instead of incandescent lamp due to its higher lumen output and efficiency. Now a days LED can be used for its higher energy savings.

In other hands, accent light plays an important role to highlight the objects individually, compared to ambient light sources in the Heritage Buildings. So, the exposure to an archival material under accent light is always more than ambient lights. From proper conservations of the artefacts, the bad as well as effects of the light need to be analysed. From earlier experiences it has been noted that fading of paintings is one of the major drawbacks of high-power artificial light sources. Thus, before applications of light source thorough studies need to be made on the fundamental colours. UV generated through artificial light sources can help in killing bacteria, etc.

The main motto of this work is to save the old artefacts (which have high antique value like paintings, sculptures, photographs, periodicals, costumes, and curio pieces etc.) from bad effects of artificial lights sources and in some places conservation of the same from Biodegradable bacteria etc. Lighting design is not only the objective of an illumination engineer, but to protect old archival materials from severe damaging effects of artificial light sources is a very much challenging work. So, effort need to find out the sources of bad effects and proper usage with optimum light energy.

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